

Impact of Teacher Training Programs on Teachers' Performance: A Case of In-Service English Language Secondary School Teachers in Pakistan

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Abstract

In-service teacher training is key for teachers to meet the challenges in education. The present research aims to explore the impacts of in-service teachers training programs on English language teaching. Moreover, the current study was to focus on the need of teachers through in-service training programs for effective teaching of English and to implement these training programs. The research was quantitative and population was secondary school English teachers in Punjab, Pakistan. 237 teachers were selected as sample of this study. Unsystematic sampling technique was used to collect the data from the respondents through survey method by using administered questionnaire. SPSS Version-25 was constructed in order to analyze the data. The findings of this research show a significant effect of training programs of teachers. The present study is helpful to guide English language teacher trainers to analyze their training programs to bring improvements in their trainings; in order to produce effective English language teachers. It is helpful to select a program for the training of in-service teachers in Punjab, Pakistan with respect to its being innovative and effective during the teaching.

Keywords: In-Service, Training Program, Teaching Performance, Secondary Level

1. Introduction

Quality of education is an important factor in the progress of any society and country, this brings a positive change in social, economic and educational life of people. The overall goal is achieved by many factors, and teacher is one of them. This research intends to highlight the usefulness of the in-service teacher training programs in lieu of the teachers for the level of secondary school. The researcher aimed to seek that those programs had an optimistic impact on English language teaching in order to check that those were implemented or not when the teacher were in classroom. The researcher assumed whether these types of training program had best and constructive impact at the level of secondary school mentor. This research is aiming to aware that without these programs one cannot teach English effectively. Arslan (2015) stated that it is indispensable in lieu of the proficiency of language. Hence, the higher management has evaluated critically these in-service training programs and their quality. Zain (2017) stated even though this is a universal truth that thinking can be changed only by the teachers in a thought-provoking manner. One can say that teacher is considered as a changing source of society. There are many teachers who are serving the nation. It has been observed that educational setup is not up to the mark. The objective of English training is to design an everlasting effect on training itself and for the next upcoming trainings. The focus of the in-service training is basically on teachers and the same alignment is then moved to learners who later chose its impact on society.

Lack of knowledge is not only the problem. Nevertheless untrained, incompetent and low paid teachers are the main problem. In past, there was no existence of teaching curricula in Asian countries and no attention was given to prove the educational system. After 1920's some attention was given to the educational sector and some policies were introduced. Keeping in view that the learning programs are mandatory for the betterment of the system. Now a day, teachers have many teaching skills and abilities. Through regular training programs, teachers learn advance methods for teaching in order to get good results (Khan & Haseeb, 2017).

A teacher should refresh his/her job requirements. Although many institutes give training to the practicing teachers where they learn different methods of teaching. The main goal of such program is to enhance their teaching abilities. The in-service training programs have got great importance all over the world. The in-service teacher training is important for long term learning. Most of the people accept this reality. To meet the existing requirements of curriculum, teacher education is necessary. To revise the whole education system, the teachers should refresh his/her knowledge and skill to meet the level of education.

2. Literature Review

Training session for in-service teachers is dire need of an hour. Only the trained teachers are producing good result. There is a difference between trained and untrained teachers. Now a days, these training programs are contributing their services for in-service as well as to pre-service teachers. In their training session many programs are included like classroom management, lesson planning, organizational service, strategy making, implementation of curriculum, methodology of teaching for the teachers etc. So, all these aspects should be in trained teachers to have a good result from learners (Arslan, 2015).

Khan and Haseeb (2017) says: the goals of teachers are so hard to recognize in the world having so many varieties of patterns and believes. According to Al-Rodzalan and Saat (2012) there are three references in teacher's educational process; the learner, the individual and national community. Reality as a whole I that both the ethical and material belief play a powerful role in establishing the future and nature of the society. According to Canado (2016), the target of education of teachers is to convert something negative into something good as a result of great experiences by giving opportunities and making a way for the student to develop their potential abilities into appropriate skills, knowledge and potential to do something based on emotional as well as logical based. Only quality teachers are nation builders.

Zein (2017) stated the education of teachers should be in such a way that provides master builders who should know that they have excess to something that cab useful for them by keeping all the aspects in mind. Nawab (2017) stated that if a competent teacher is required, there

is a possibility of getting describes results that will be fair enough. According to Moodley (2013) there is always a desire to have a training session whether the institutions have all the necessary arrangement like syllabus, classrooms, setup of students sitting, labs and building etc. The teaching setup will be unproductive and wastage of time if the teacher does not recognize his/her teaching responsibilities. According to Haider and Ali (2012) teacher training program was established in Karachi and Lahore: training was in formal manner. According to Savolainen et al (2012) to improve teacher's professional knowledge by following their primary skill endorsements in order to educate children in a more effective way (Giraldo, 2014).

According to Aziz and Akhtar (2014) learning is a lifelong or lifetime process. In-service education, a teacher may participate to upgrade their professional knowledge, skills, and competencies in teaching profession for a longer period of time. Khattak et al (2011) stated that the teacher who are in-service they also need professional educational improvement to upgrade them. Rehman (2011) states that there is dire need of in-service teacher's training programs. Polat and Mahalingappa (2013) states that there is a huge significance of professional education for professional teachers that is accepted and we can see in many popular textbooks, articles and in research studies. Teachers are actually the hub of educational development.

Liu and Kkeinsasser (2015) said the purpose of these type of trainings are to promote not only the skills of teachers but also for their promotion in their professional life. This can only be achieved through proper planning, well ordered instructions within the educational setup. To keep these points in mind, the researchers are trying to research on the abilities of teachers. Training session should be organized in order to the role-shift of the teachers. According to Zein (2016) dire need of these sessions of training designed for qualified in-service teachers in different circumstances e.g., different activities are given to qualified teachers, they can join a group where they can be member. In this way, his/her situation has been changed, definitely this will help them in the sense of learning new methodologies, activities and skills. This is also effective and provides help for fresh teachers to learn the novae points.

According to Azam et al (2014) rapid explosion in the learning process and knowledge, one session of training for in-service teacher is not sufficient for whole of their teaching career. There must be a chain of training sessions which should be implemented time to time to enhance their professional skill. According to Tzivinikou (2015) teacher's competency matters a lot. Only in this way, institutes can achieve their objectives. Burgess (2013) stated that setup of building, classrooms, syllabus and books are not sufficient for having a command on knowledge. Competent teachers are required who are fully trained to deliver knowledge in a useful and efficient way.

2.1 Problem Statement

Having glance on previous researches, training programs are being conducted to enhance the skills of in-service teachers. The researcher aims to seek the current scenario of the effect of in-service training programs and specially refer to the implementation on the learners in the classroom. Although government used many methods for the development of teaching process through teacher training programs, yet not put into consideration. The present study precedes to evaluate these programs of teacher training. The overall purpose of the research is to scrutinize the effect of training programs of in-service teachers to assess the learner's achievements.

2.2 Hypothesis

- HA1. A significance impact of teacher training on the performance of the secondary school in-service teachers.
 HA2. A Significance difference between trained and untrained teachers regarding teacher training program.
 HA3. A Significance difference between male and female teachers regarding teacher training program.

3. Methodology

The present research aims to scrutinize the impacts of teacher training programs on English language teaching. Moreover, the current study was to focus on the need of teachers through in-service training programs for effective teaching of English and to implement these training programs. In this study teachers training programs was used as independent variable whereas teachers' performance as dependent variable. The research was cross-sectional and quantitative. The secondary school English teachers in Punjab, Pakistan were the population and 237 (Female =129, Male=108 and Trained = 142, Untrained = 95) respondents were selected as a sample for this study. Random sampling technique was used to collect the data from the respondents through survey method by using administered questionnaire whereas, five points Likert scale 1. Strongly Disagree to 5. Strongly Agree was used. The reliability was assessed by Using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient that was greater than 0.7 as threshold value by (Nunnally, 1978). SPSS Version-25 was constructed in order to analyze the data through descriptive and inferential statistics, i.e., M, SD, independent sample t-test, Pearson Correlation and Regression analysis.

4. Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Constructs	M	SD
Teacher training programs	4.38	.83
Teachers' performance	3.84	.97

Table 2: Independent Sample t-test

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig
Training Programs	Male	108	4.59	1.23	2.86	.02*
	Female	129	3.21	1.47	1.98	
Teaching Performance	Male	108	4.64	1.67	3.47	.00**
	Female	129	3.09	1.21	3.26	

Sig < .05

Table 3: Independent Sample t-test

Variables	Category	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig
Training Programs	Trained	142	4.63	1.19	2.89	.00**
	Untrained	95	3.37	1.53	1.87	
Teaching Performance	Trained	142	4.79	1.57	2.59	.00**
	Untrained	95	3.23	1.17	2.26	

Sig < .05

Table 4: Pearson Correlation

Exogenous Variables	Teacher training programs	Teachers' performance
Teacher training programs	1	
Teachers' performance	.586(**)	1

.00-.2 (Weak), .3-.6 (Moderate), .7-.9 (Strong)

Table. 5: Regression Analysis

Model	Constructs	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
Teachers' Performance	(Constant)				
	Teacher training program	.040	.162	4.09	.00**

Dependent Variable: TP, Sig < .05

4. Conclusion and Discussion

It was finalized that the teachers of secondary school were well aware about the importance of teaching training programs to boost the teaching performance of in-service teachers. A significance difference occurs among the female and male teachers whereas, mean score of 'male' was greater than female that means that male teachers have good performance as compared to female teachers through teaching training. Moreover, a significant difference was found among the trained and untrained teachers. Whereas, mean score of trained teachers was greater than untrained, that means that trained teachers have good performance, positive and moderate impact of teachers training programs on in-service teacher's performance as compared to untrained teachers through teaching training. Furthermore, a positive correlation between teacher training programs as well as teachers job performance. Additionally, there was a positive and moderate impact of training programs on the performance of in-service teachers.

This research portrait that a trained in-service teacher uses innovative method of digging out the maximum results from the learners. Also have a gut to tackle with the new situation faced in teaching while untrained in-service teachers are lacking this ability. This research gives picture that learners are suffering because of the lack of training programs of teachers. Low individual attention is given to the learners by untrained in-service teachers. Therefore, lack of considerations is given to teach the English subject as it could be taught. Hence, it is proved that trained in-service teachers are striking competent for better understanding of knowledge. They adorn the learners with updated skills and knowledge.

The result shows that there is a difference in trained in-service teachers and un-trained in-service teachers: in presenting and explanation ability, understanding how to deliver lectures in an efficient manner, managing classroom discipline, applied contemporary knowledge, new ideas in teaching, in adopting innovative techniques, provision of friendly environment. As well as trained in-service teachers selects appropriate and relevant teaching material to meet the challenges of the world in the scenario of gaining knowledge. Moreover, they have a linguistics proficiency and have a command on language which is a basic element in English language teaching.

On the other hand, in a slight effort has been completed regarding the training of in-service teachers in regard to English language. But numerous is still needed in this regard. The study delves deep into bringing out the variations in the teaching styles of both the genders in teaching and highlight the positive impact of training programs of in-service teachers during practicing the teaching as well as in the achievements of learners.

5. Future research

It will help the future scholars to understand the need of training programs of in-service teachers in Pakistan context, what kind of diction is used and what garners attention of masses used by trained and untrained teacher. Albeit Literature will be amongst primary source to utilize this research with more efficacy. The further study should be conducted with other variables that enhance the teacher's performance and in different areas of the country.

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